

Navigating the Data Patchwork

Strategies for Integrating Metadata Catalogs, Data Publications, and Archives

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Abstract

In modern science, the integrity and utility of research outputs critically depend on both data and metadata. **Data** comprise the primary outputs of experiments, simulations, or analyses — structured or unstructured information directly reflecting observed phenomena. **Metadata**, by contrast, describe the origin, structure, semantics, and context of those data, enabling their interpretation, discovery, and reuse. Although often treated as secondary, metadata are essential for ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), which have become a cornerstone of modern data stewardship [1]. A failure to adequately define or manage metadata leads to data silos, poor reproducibility, and limited interoperability [2].

To address this, we propose a solution based on the decoupling yet tight linkage of a data and a metadata repository, following the principle of “separation of concerns” [3]. In this model, raw and processed data are published in scalable data repositories along with bibliographic metadata, while rich, structured, and extensible domain-specific metadata is maintained in a dedicated metadata repository. Linking mechanisms (e.g. JSON-LD, RDF) together with persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs, Handles) and metadata schemata (e.g. DataCite), ensuring integrity and support machine-actionable workflows across the research lifecycle [4], [5], [6].

At Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR), this modular architecture is implemented through the integration of two distinct but interconnected components: the institutional data repository RODARE [7] and the domain-oriented metadata catalogue SciCat [8] (see Figure 1). RODARE is based on the Invenio framework [9] developed by CERN and provides a robust platform for the long-term archiving and dissemination of digital research objects, including datasets, software, and publications. It assigns persistent identifiers (DOIs), supports access control policies, and ensures compliance with institutional policies [10], [11] and FAIR data management guidelines. Complementing this, SciCat serves as a scientific metadata catalogue tailored to the needs

Figure 1. Overview of the (semi)-automated ingestion of metadata from our internal domain-driven applications into our public accessible metadata catalogue SciCat and the interlinked data in our data repository RODARE.

of experimental and computational research workflows. SciCat captures rich, schema-based metadata at the time of data acquisition or processing, enabling fine-grained search, filtering, and workflow integration. The linkage between RODARE and SciCat is established through shared persistent identifiers, allowing each platform to serve its core function: SciCat for active metadata curation and workflow integration, and RODARE for long-term storage and publication of the datasets.

To streamline metadata generation and reduce manual curation effort, HZDR has developed a set of tools for automated metadata ingestion into SciCat. One key component for the scientific metadata is the electronic labbook at HZDR: A customized Semantic MediaWiki [12] instance, used by researchers to document experimental configurations, instrument settings, and contextual details in a structured, human-readable format. Through template-based forms and semantic annotations, this MediaWiki setup enables the capture and extraction of relevant metadata elements, which are then programmatically transformed and ingested into SciCat via REST API. These automated pipelines capture domain-specific data at the point of creation, such as beamline settings, sample parameters or simulation inputs, and store them according to a community-specific schema. The additional subsequent provision of access to directories in the HZDR network is provided via HELIPORT [13].

In summary, the approach can serve as an illustrative example of a RDM infrastructure combining separate data and metadata services into an overall concept.

Keywords: Data management, Metadata, Research Infrastructure, SciCat, Invenio, Data publication

Resources

- *RODARE Repository Service at HZDR* [14]

The institutional Data repository RODARE (Rossendorf Data Repository) hosted at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden – Rossendorf (HZDR) as a citable service.

- *SciCat Service at HZDR* [15]
The metadata catalogue SciCat hosted at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden – Rossendorf (HZDR) as a citable service.
- *HELIPORT Service at HZDR* [16]
The data management guidance system HELIPORT hosted at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden – Rossendorf (HZDR) as a citable service.
- *HELIPORT Software Publication* [17]
The software publication of the HELIPORT source code.

Author contributions

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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